

TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF KNITTED FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the tensile deformation behavior of glass/epoxy warp knitted fabric reinforced composites was studied, and compared with that of woven fabric composites and of the epoxy matrix. In monotonic loading conditions, the tensile curve of all these materials is strongly nonlinear. The time-dependency of the deformation is shown to be small. Cyclic tensile tests revealed that the epoxy deforms elastically, while the deformation of the composites is partially elastic (nonlinear) and partially inelastic. These inelastic deformations could be attributed to damage development and/or local plastic deformation. Recommendations are formulated to test the E-modulus and Poisson's ratio of knitted fabric composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Textile reinforcements for composite materials become more popular nowadays, at the expense of laminates made out of unidirectional laminae. The reason for this is mainly the higher damage tolerance of textile composites, which is assessed to be more important than the consequent loss in stiffness and strength compared to UD-laminates. A second important stimulus for textile composites is the need for higher production rates. In particular multiaxial, woven and knitted fabrics are attractive reinforcement materials because they can be formed into a 3-dimensional shape in a simple deepdraw-like production step. However, double-curved shapes such as boxes or cylinders can best be covered without wrinkles by knitted fabrics. The use of knitted fabrics reduces the mechanical properties of the composite compared to woven fabrics, but they perform still better than short fiber reinforcements [1,2]. This relatively good mechanical behavior of knitted fabric composites is recognized nowadays and there is a growing interest to extend the area of textile reinforcements to knitted fabrics.

In view of the unfamiliarity with this new class of composite materials, the testing of the mechanical properties needs some consideration. In this paper, the tensile deformation behavior of knitted fabric composites is studied. Special attention is paid to determine to what degree the deformation is elastic. Further, the effect of test speed is looked at. In literature, the specimen size effect was investigated for composites with braided, woven and knitted fabric reinforcements [3-5]. No apparent effect of size on the stiffness and strength was found, as long as the specimen width contains a sufficient number of textile repeating units. Masters *et.al.* [3] showed that within

one unit cell, the deformation of a 2-D braided composite is strongly heterogeneous. This has important implications when small strain gages are used.

2. MATERIALS USED

Three types of warp knitted fabrics were used in this study. They are made out of glass fiber and produced on a double guide bar knitting machine. Knit type BS is presented in Fig. 1. It is formed by a lapping movement over 3 needles across, resulting in a closed 3-and-1 warp knit, also called a 3-needle satin [6]. Similarly, type BST consists out of 2 sets of yarns, both making the 3-and-1 lapping movement but to opposite directions. Type BD is a 2-and-1 knit. Due to the different fiber orientation distribution in the fabrics, the respective composites will show a different anisotropy in the mechanical properties. In order to have a valid reference for the tensile behavior of the knitted fabric composites, a plane woven fabric composite was fabricated as well.

As a matrix material, epoxy F533 produced by Hexcel was used. The composites were cured in an autoclave during 1 hour at 125°C, under vacuum and a pressure of 3 bar. Also pure epoxy plates were made in a vacuum oven at 125°C.

Figure 1. Loop structure of type BS warp knitted fabric.

3. MONOTONIC TENSILE TESTS

3.1 TEST PROCEDURE

ASTM standard D3039-93 for testing the tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials was followed as much as possible. Specimen dimensions were taken: 210x25 mm, with a tested length of 150 mm. Always a longitudinal and a transverse extensometer was attached to the specimen, both having a gauge length of 25 mm. The extensometers were placed symmetrically about the mid-span, mid-width location. A gauge length of 25 mm contained always more than 14 repeating units of the knitted fabrics and 8 for the woven fabric. This should be enough to average out the heterogeneous deformation within one unit cell [3].

Each material was tested in X-, Y- and D-direction, that stand for wale (or warp), course (or weft) and 45° (or diagonal). At least 5 specimens were tested for each specimen type. An Instron type 4505 testing machine was used with a hydraulic gripping system. The use of end tabs

showed not to be necessary to prevent failure in the grips. Head displacement rate was set to 2 mm/min.

3.2 TENSILE CURVES

Typical tensile curves of the knitted fabric composites are shown in Fig. 2. The curves are nonlinear, even at very small strains. This becomes clear when the slope (being the tangent modulus) is drawn versus the longitudinal strain (Fig. 3a). Fig. 3b shows the variation of the tangent Poisson's ratio with longitudinal strain. The values are normalised to the value at 0.1% strain ($E_{0.1}$ and $\nu_{0.1}$). The tensile curves of the woven fabric composites and those of the epoxy showed a similar, nonlinear behavior (Fig. 4). However, the nonlinearity is smaller for the pure epoxy, and for the woven fabric composite in warp (X) and weft (Y) direction. The graphs show that for the tested materials no 'knee point' up to which the stiffness is constant, can be found. Such a knee point is commonly encountered for woven composites [7], and was also found by Ramakrishna and Hull [8] for carbon/epoxy weft knitted fabric composites. Their tensile curves

Figure 2. Tensile curves of type BD knitted fabric composites (X= wale, Y= course, D= diagonal direction).

Figure 3. (a) Normalised tangent moduli and (b) normalised tangent Poisson's ratio vs. strain of type BD knitted fabric composites. $E_{0.1}$ and $\nu_{0.1}$ are the tangent E-modulus and Poisson's ratio at 0.1% longitudinal strain, respectively.

were linear up to about 0.3% after which debonding and matrix cracking occurred. Also Mayer [9] found an originally linear tensile curve for carbon/epoxy knitted fabric composites. Possible reasons for the absence of a knee point at the tested composites are the different constituent materials (glass/epoxy) or the different textile structure (e.g. smaller loops that create higher stress concentrations).

In general, nonlinear behavior can originate from various sources. For most composites, nonlinear *elastic* response stems from the nonlinearity of the matrix, in tensile but mainly in shear. Micromechanical models have been developed to calculate the influence of the matrix nonlinearity on the elastic properties of laminates and woven fabric composites [7,10-13]. Apart from elastic nonlinearity, also *inelastic* behavior gives rise to nonlinearities. On the one hand, some matrices deform partially plastically, which is as a rule nonlinear. On the other hand, damage mechanisms such as fiber/matrix debonding and matrix cracking are encountered in many composites and are believed to be the main reasons for nonlinear deformation of short fiber reinforced composites [14,15]. In addition, some matrices exhibit a considerable time-dependent behavior, also a source of nonlinearities. In what follows, we try to find out which of these mechanisms play a part in the tested knitted and woven fabric composites.

Figure 4. Normalised tangent modulus vs. strain of (a) woven fabric composites and (b) epoxy.

3.3 INFLUENCE OF TEST SPEED

Monotonic tensile tests at different test speeds were performed on knitted fabric composites and on the epoxy, so as to get an idea of the time-dependency of the deformation. Knitted fabric composites type BS were tested at crosshead displacement rates of 1 and 20 mm/min, epoxy specimens at 2 and 10 mm/min. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding tensile curves. Each curve is an average of at least 3 specimens, cut out of the same plate and tested under identical test conditions. The rate-effect at both epoxy and composite is small compared to the experimental scatter. So, the tensile behavior probably is time-dependent, but the measured time-dependency seems too small to account fully for the nonlinear deformation behavior of these materials.

Figure 5. Influence of test speed on the tensile curves of (a) type BS knitted fabric composites (Y-direction) and (b) epoxy.

4. CYCLIC TENSILE TESTS

4.1 TENSILE CURVES

In order to get an idea to what extent the deformation is elastic, cyclic tests were performed on all the knitted and woven fabric composites, and on the epoxy. The specimens used were identical as for the monotonic tests. Specimens were loaded up to a specified strain at a crosshead displacement rate of 2 mm/min and then unloaded at the same rate to zero load. Three such cycles were performed. Successively a specimen was loaded to increasing cycle strain levels (0.2%, 0.5% and 1%). The cyclic tensile curves of a typical knitted fabric composite for cycles up to 0.2% and 0.5% are shown in Fig. 6. When loaded up to 0.5%, the knitted fabric composites clearly show a residual strain of about 0.05% after unloading. This residual strain increases when loaded up to 1%. At the same time, the hysteresis increases. This indicates that, a big part of the deformation being elastic, some irreversible mechanisms take place in the material. On the other hand, cycling up to 0.2% strain doesn't seem to produce much inelastic deformation. In all cases, the second and third cycle were almost identical. This means that after the first cycle, the material behaves elastically (*i.e.* reversible), but with significant hysteresis.

Fig. 7 shows the cyclic tensile curves for the woven fabric composites (0.5% cycles) and the epoxy (1% cycles). For the woven fabric composites the residual strain as well as the hysteresis is rather small in warp (X) and weft (Y) direction, but large under 45° (D). The epoxy can be considered elastic, at least up to strains of 1%.

4.2 DISCUSSION

Based on the results of both the monotonic and cyclic tests, we can draw some conclusions regarding the origin of the nonlinear behavior of the materials under study. As already mentioned, the pure epoxy is shown to be elastic, at least up to strains of 1% (the ultimate tensile strain of this epoxy was about 3.2%).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Cyclic tensile curves of type BS knitted fabric composites in X- and Y-direction for 3 cycles up to (a) 0.2% and (b) 0.5%.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Cyclic tensile curves of (a) woven fabric composites, 0.5% cycle and (b) epoxy, 1% cycle.

The deformation of the knitted fabric composites contains an inelastic part when the material is deformed to 0.5% strain, while the deformation is shown to be elastic up to 0.2%. The nonlinear *elasticity* is probably mainly caused by the nonlinear behavior of the epoxy in shear (which was not tested), because in tensile the nonlinearity of the epoxy is rather small (see Fig. 4b). The *inelastic* part in the deformation must be due to damage phenomena and/or plastic deformation. Although the epoxy doesn't show any plastic behavior till 1%, local plastic deformation at strain concentration points could occur. It has to be kept in mind that inside a yarn, the fibre volume fraction can be as high as 80%. At such high fibre contents, an external load together with thermal stresses give rise to high stress concentrations, leading to early plastic deformation and/or damage development. Which of the two occurs first depends on the interface strength. Possible damage modes are fiber/matrix debonding or matrix cracking. In this, the knitted fabric composite is much comparable to a randomly oriented short fiber composite because of their similar fiber orientation distribution. However, damage development in short fiber composites is believed to be even more severe because of the additional harmful effect of the fiber ends.

By polishing the sides of the tensile specimens, we tried to find out whether possible damage phenomena initiated from the sides. The tensile curves of polished knitted fabric composites (type BS) didn't change however, nor changed the ultimate tensile strength. It could therefore be concluded that the damage is not initiated at the specimen sides.

The woven fabric composites when tested parallel to the fibers (X,Y), deform nearly elastically. Testing under 45° (D) results in much more inelastic deformation and a much higher amount of hysteresis. The reason for this is that the matrix takes up a bigger part of the load (which is shear), with a higher nonlinear elasticity and earlier and heavier damage development and/or plastic deformation as a result.

By considering the foregoing materials as laminates, it is possible to approximate theoretically the effect of matrix nonlinearity, as well as the effects of cracking on the stiffness of the composite. Woven fabric composites can be roughly modelled as a (0/90)_s or a (±45)_s laminate, while knitted fabric composites can be described as (±15_k/±45_l/±75_m)_s laminates, with the fractions k, l and m determined on the base of fiber orientation distribution measurements [16]. Results of these calculations will be published shortly.

5. DETERMINATION OF THE ELASTIC CONSTANTS

A tensile test is usually meant to determine the ultimate tensile strength, the E-modulus and - in case two extensometers are used - Poisson's ratio. The nonlinear character of the tensile curve complicates the determination of the elastic constants somewhat. Ideally, the tangent modulus at 0% strain (E₀) should be taken as the E-modulus. Direct measurement of this value is not possible however due to inaccuracies at the start-up of a measurement caused by backlash, specimen curvature or initial grip misalignment. When the ultimate tensile strain is larger than 1.2%, ASTM standard D3039-93 recommends the use of strain and stress data in the range between 0.1% and 0.6% longitudinal strain. For the tested knitted and woven fabric composites however, in this range the deformation is not perfectly elastic anymore. The cyclic tests described in chapter 4 showed that up to 0.2% the deformation is nearly reversible. Therefore, we propose to determine the E-modulus and Poisson's ratio as a tangent value at 0.1% strain. This could be done for example by a linear regression between 0.09 and 0.11% strain, if enough data points are available in this range. For each material, it is recommended to perform some cyclic tests too, to verify whether the material deforms elastically up to 0.1%. If not, a smaller reference strain that still can be measured accurately should be chosen.

At this time, shear tests on knitted fabric composites are being performed with the 3-Rail Shear and the Iosipescu test method. As could be expected, also in shear the deformation is strongly nonlinear. Results of monotonic and cyclic tests will be reported later.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the tensile deformation behavior of knitted and woven fabric composites was studied. Both monotonic and cyclic tests were performed on 3 types of glass/epoxy warp knitted fabric and 1 type of plane woven fabric composites. Monotonic tests showed a strongly nonlinear tensile behavior. For none of the materials a linear part in the tensile curve could be recognized. Also the pure epoxy showed to deform nonlinearly. Cyclic tests revealed that the deformation of the epoxy was reversible, while the knitted and woven fabric composites exhibited some irreversible deformation. This was attributed to damage accumulation such as fiber/matrix debonding and matrix cracks, and local plastic deformation. Test speed had only a minor influence on the tensile curves. Based on these results, it is suggested to determine the elastic constants as a tangent value at a longitudinal strain of 0.1%. It is recommended however always to perform some cyclic tests to verify whether the deformation is still elastic up to this strain.

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8. REFERENCES

1. B. Gommers, T.K. Wang, I. Verpoest, Mechanical properties of warp knitted fabric reinforced composites, Proc. 40th Int. SAMPE Symp., Anaheim, USA, May 8-11 (1995).
2. I. Verpoest, J. Dendauw, Mechanical properties of knitted glass fibre/epoxy resin laminates, Proc. 37th Int. SAMPE Symp., Anaheim, USA, March 9-12, 369-377 (1992).
3. J.E. Masters, P.G. Ifju, M.J. Fedro, Development of test methods for textile composites, Proc. Fiber-Tex, NASA, Philadelphia, USA, Oct. 27-29, 249-269 (1992).
4. P. Davies, D. Choqueuse, M. Delbury, J. Deverité, Scale effects in the determination of tensile and shear properties of marine composites, Proc. Eur. Conf. on Comp. Testing and Standardisation (ECCM-CTS2), Hamburg, Germany, Sept. 13-15, 277-286 (1994).
5. H. Hamada, A. Fujita, M. Inoda, Z. Maekawa, Effects of the specimen width on the tensile behavior of textile composites, Proc. Eur. Conf. on Comp. Testing and Standardisation (ECCM-CTS2), Hamburg, Germany, Sept. 13-15, 287-294 (1994).
6. S. Raz, Warp knitting production, Melliand Textilberichte GmbH, Heidelberg (1987).
7. T. Ishikawa, T-W. Chou, Nonlinear behavior of woven fabric composites, *J. Comp. Mtls.*, **17**, 399-413 (1983).
8. S. Ramakrishna, D. Hull, Tensile behaviour of knitted carbon-fibre fabric/epoxy laminates - Part I: experimental, *Comp. Sci. and Techn.*, **50**, 237-247 (1994).
9. J. Mayer, Gestricken aus Kohlenstoffasern für biokompatible Verbundwerkstoffe, dargestellt an einer homoelastischen Osteosyntheseplatte, PhD thesis, ETH Zürich (1994).
10. J. Aboudi, The nonlinear behavior of unidirectional and laminated composites - A micromechanical approach, *J. Reinf. Plastics and Comp.*, **9**, 13-32 (1990).
11. S.R. Frost, An approximate theory for predicting the moduli of uni-directional laminates with non-linear stress/strain behavior, *J. Comp. Mtls.*, **24**, 269-292 (1990).
12. W. Sun, S.C. Khatri, A.C.W. Lau, M.J. Koczak, Nonlinear material modeling and experimental characterization of graphite/PPS and glass/PPS thermoplastic matrix composites, *J. Thermoplastic Comp. Mtls.*, **5**, 166-180 (1992).
13. H.T. Hahn, Nonlinear behavior of laminated composites, *J. Comp. Mtls.*, **7**, 257-271 (1973).
14. K-Y. Hour, H. Sehitoglu, Damage development in a short fiber reinforced composite, *J. Comp. Mtls.*, **27**, 782-805 (1993).
15. C.Y. Chen, C.L. Tucker III, Mechanical property predictions for short fiber/brittle matrix composites, *J. Reinf. Plastics and Comp.*, **3**, 120-129 (1984).
16. B. Gommers, S. Gijbels, I. Verpoest, P. Van Houtte, Modelling the elastic properties of knitted fabric reinforced composites, to be published.